

Prospects and Challenges of Smart Teaching and Learning in Nigeria's Tertiary Institutions

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Abstract

Purpose: *This paper explores the prospects and challenges of smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions.*

Methodology: *Typology design of conceptual paper was used to identify, review and analyse the available literature on smart technologies, smart teaching and learning and some high-end technologies catalyzing teaching and learning.*

Findings: *Reviews revealed that artificial intelligence, cloud computing, internet-of-education-things, smartboards, learning management systems and learning analytics are used for smart teaching and learning to promote equity in teaching and learning, enhance efficiency and effectiveness in teaching and learning and eliminate geographical barriers. It was further found that the potential of smart teaching and learning cannot be harnessed because of inadequate ICT/digital literacy, poor Internet bandwidth, fear of change and comfortability with the traditional teaching and learning are the banes of smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions.*

Conclusion: *Smart teaching and learning have provided platforms for teaching and learning to occur in alignment with teachers' and learners' peculiarities, making teaching and learning engaging and stimulating for 21st-century teachers and learners.*

Study Type: *Conceptual study*

Keywords: *Teaching, learning, high-end technologies, smart technologies, smart teaching and learning, tertiary institutions, Nigeria*

Introduction

Tertiary institutions are centres devoted to teaching, learning, research, community development and services. Their roles in the development of all societies have been hugely felt by providing pathways for the discovery and harnessing of human potential, thereby contributing to the growth of the quality of human capital in the societies in which they are domiciled (and beyond). The crucial roles of tertiary institutions have made them highly flexible, causing them to always strive to adopt and adapt to emerging processes of teaching, learning and imparting knowledge.

In the contemporary world, it is apt to say that some developed countries are living in a smart society; a society permeated by smart technologies, in which human actions are frequently mediated by smart

tools and the objects they encounter are often shaped by the intervention of sophisticated technologies. With the new knowledge and improved technology, teaching and learning in tertiary institutions have also changed drastically (Phuapan, Viriyavejakul & Pimdee, 2016).

The 21st-century tertiary education has been highly revolutionised, requiring that the teachers and learners must have the suitable skills to access, assess, use, manage and enrich the vastness of their knowledge through smart technologies. High-end technologies have become a key element in teaching and learning across the different educational stages that has been addressed since the last decade of the twentieth century within the field of open, distance and digital education (Lankshear & Knobel, 2016; David-West, 2022).

Smart teaching and learning evolved as a result of advanced latest technologies that make teaching and learning possible by relying on sophisticated machines that are programmed with innate intelligence to facilitate teaching and learning with little or no intervention of teachers and facilitators (Igwe & Sulyman, 2022). Orji and Anyira (2021) claimed that smart teaching and learning are smart because they rely on the use of machines programmed with human intelligence to perform teaching and learning functions as if they are trained teachers and learners. Smart teaching and learning are a conglomeration of hardware and software installed to act as teachers and learners in smart patterns.

The rapid growth and advancement in technologies have made smart teaching and learning a subject of discussion in academics. However, its adoption and implementation are peculiar, being determined by some demographics and social dynamics, indicating the readiness of a society to shift with the paradigm dominating the education sector. Acknowledging the impact of some demographics and social dynamics in following the trend of smart teaching and learning becomes the basis for this paper to explore the prospects and challenges of smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions.

Teaching and learning are indispensable educational activities in every society. They are vehicles for reforming people's characters and reprogramming their minds for creative, innovative and novel causes that can positively impact humanity. Teaching and learning have been heavily performed through traditional processes since they were formalized, where teachers and learners need to appear physically before they can teach and learn.

The evolution of information and communication technology has forced tertiary institutions to adjust and redesign their teaching and learning processes. This was further deepened by the transitioning of ICT to more sophisticated machines and gadgets, known as high-end or emerging technologies. These technologies make teaching and learning seamless, making the physical appearance of both the teachers and learners in tertiary institutions needless. High-end technologies paved the way for what is today known as smart teaching and learning. However, preliminary findings by these researchers have revealed that the prospects of smart teaching and learning in tertiary institutions in Nigeria might not be harnessed because of some problems ranging from inadequate ICT infrastructure, over-reliance on the traditional teaching and learning styles, fear of and reluctance to change, poor Internet bandwidth and inadequate ICT/digital literacy skills. This underscores why this paper will be exploring the prospects and challenges of smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions.

Generally, this paper will provide insights into the prospects and challenges of smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions. It will offer clear explanations of the concept of smart teaching and learning, reveal some high-end technologies used for smart teaching and learning in tertiary institutions, and discuss the prospects of smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions and the challenges of smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions.

Methodology

This paper adopts a typology and case study designs to identify, review and analyse the available literature on smart technologies, smart teaching and learning and some high-end technologies catalysing teaching and learning. Jaakkola (2020) opines that a typology paper provides a more precise and

nuanced understanding of a phenomenon or concept understudying, pinpointing and justifying key dimensions that distinguish the variants of the concept. The typology approach helps this paper explain the evolving nature of smart teaching and learning by logically and causally combining them into a coherent and explanatory set of types. Similarly, a case study was adopted to report the status of smart teaching and learning at Kwara State University, narrating its potential and current challenges to its seamless deployment.

Concept of Smart Teaching and Learning

The concept of smart teaching and learning comes into being as a result of the aggregation of the words 'smart,' 'teaching,' and 'learning.' Adetayo, Adeniran and Gbotosho (2021) asserted that the word 'smart' has several connotations, such as efficient, sustainable, equitable, habitable, instrumented and networked, while Orji and Anyira (2021) viewed 'smart' as having or showing a quick-witted intelligence. The word 'smart' refers mainly to efficiency due to the use of technologies and to automatization of processes to facilitate the working and everyday environment (Freyberg, 2019).

The connotations of 'smart' can simply be summarised as being smart, which amounts to intelligence and a quick cognitive capacity. To minimise the misconceptions of 'smart,' its relevance to this context will hereby be justified within the purview of the intelligent aspect of its meaning. Psychologists such as Daniel Goleman and Howard Gardner have defined intelligence in different ways, with all of them basing their definitions on contexts. Sulyman (2022) therefore aptly sees intelligence as the ability to be aware or sensitive to a particular condition, identify the factors associated with it and use those factors for decision-making.

'Teaching' and 'learning' are essential aspects of education. They encompass the processes at which instructions are being delivered to influence and change one's impressions, perceptions and opinions about something. It usually involves both the teachers and learners. Teachers are the ones providing the instructions, trying to shape and influence the opinions and perceptions of the learners, while the learners are the recipients of the instructions being delivered by the teachers. The transitioning of teaching and learning from the traditional process to the one aided by technologies is known as smart teaching.

Smart teaching and learning environments, sometimes used to refer to as smart education, represent a new wave of educational systems, involving an effective and efficient interplay of pedagogy, technology and their fusion towards the betterment of teaching and learning processes (Shoikova, Nikolov & Kovatcheva, 2017). Smart teaching and learning are not just about technology. It is also about new teaching and learning approaches. Increasing internet speeds and storage areas, together with the advances in cloud computing technologies, make the information available to everybody, from everywhere, at all times. Traditional training and education methodologies, in which the instructor explains the subject in the classroom and the students complete the exercises at home, are replaced by new learning approaches such as distant learning, mobile learning (m-learning), personalized learning, flipped and blended learning, social collaborative learning, game-based learning and others (Demir, 2021). Smart teaching and learning are products of technological development, where new technologies simply reinforce the old ways of teaching and learning. This pattern of teaching and learning encompasses a paradigm shift from traditional education and training practices to more advanced approaches and practices in line with the digital age. It requires the use of information technologies for new or improved learning and teaching approaches. In smart teaching and learning, the learner should be autonomous and collaborative in addition to being an efficient technology user (Demir, 2021).

Smart teaching and learning use diverse technologies (combinatorial optimization, machine learning, big data, data visualisation, internet-of-education-things, learning analytics and others) to enhance the quality of teaching and learning. They exploit educational technology (PowerPoint Presentation), Learning Management System Platforms (Moodle, smartboard), Chat Rooms, E-Mail, Internet

Connection, Multimedia Technology, Online Activity (online teaching, online discussion, online information searching) and Video Conferences to enrich teaching and learning (Díaz-Parra et al., 2022). Smart teaching and learning ecosystems integrate smart technologies to personalise and self-regulate teaching and learning. The features of smart teaching and learning include a self-directed platform, motivated, adaptive, resource-enriched and technology-embedded, formal and informal learning, social and collaborative learning, personalised and situated learning, and application and content focus (Lee, 2015).

Hwang (2015) posited that a smart teaching and learning environment must be designed to detect and take into account real-world contexts, situate learners in real-world scenarios, adapt learning interfaces for individual learners, adapt learning tasks for individual learners, provide personalised feedback or guidance, provide learning guidance or support across disciplines, provide learning guidance or support across contexts, recommend learning tools or strategies, consider learners' online learning status, consider learners' real-world learning status, facilitate both formal and informal learning, take multiple personal and environmental factors into consideration, interact with users via multiple channels, provide learners with support in advance, across real and virtual contexts.

High-end Technologies Used for Smart Teaching and Learning in Tertiary Institutions

The alarming rate of advancement in technologies has become a challenge for tertiary institutions to meet up with. High-end technologies come with various features, guidelines and functions that make them thoroughly considered for quality, efficient and effective teaching and learning. Based on the empirical evidence (Pal & Sharma, 2017; Ramasany & Kadry, 2021), the following high-end technologies can be deployed for smart teaching and learning:

1. **Cloud Computing:** Alizahed and Hassan (2013) described cloud computing as a virtual platform that is user-friendly, and permits on-demand access to shared computing resources like storage, servers, networks, applications and services that are fast to launch and implement with minimum interference from management or services providers. Cloud computing is a very flexible model that allows tertiary institutions to build or prepare their own application, which can be used by other tertiary institutions through the Internet and also provides a common computing platform (Dastagiri & Kumar, 2017). It is an evolving technology that offers opportunities to tertiary institutions providing limitless or timeless services to learners to store and access educational content and information on the cloud.
2. **Internet-of-things (IoT)/Internet-of-education-things (IoEdT):** IoT refers to the evolutionary stage of the Internet that makes a global communication infrastructure between humans and machines. IoT constructs the global infrastructure to change the fundamental aspects of human lives, which teaching and learning are a part of (Igwe & Sulyman, 2022). IoEdT is a digital interconnection of not computational and computational education-objects using sensors and RFID technology with the Internet. IoEdT is related to the processes and activities of education, research, administration and other aspects related to the institutions of higher education's strategies for teaching and learning (smart learning), using high-tech services (smart campus), the interaction between student-professor (smart classroom), and the design and development of multimedia contents for learning (smart education) (Díaz-Parra et al., 2022).
3. **Artificial Intelligence (AI):** AI is also known as machine intelligence. It is an intelligence demonstrated by machines in contrast to the natural intelligence displayed by humans and other animals. Some of the activities that AI is designed to do in teaching and learning are speech recognition, learning, planning, perception, logical reasoning and problem-solving (Igwe & Sulyman, 2022). The algorithms embedded in AI make it capable of predicting and adapting, making decisions on its own, continuously learning, forward-looking, motion and perception (Saleh, 2019).

Some other aspects of AI useful for smart teaching and learning are robotics, virtual/augmented reality and machine learning.

4. **Smart learning or Learning analytics (LA):** Learning analytics is the collection, analysis, and use of the data accumulated about learning processes. LA uses statistical techniques, machine-learning approaches, and data visualisation techniques to provide knowledge that will help to optimise student performance, highlight students' problems (identify the students' problems and needs), monitor their efforts and progress, analyse the evaluation process, discover the learning styles of the students, determine reforms on the learning processes and monitor the learning process in the smart classroom to improve the pedagogical strategies and tune-up educational platforms (Díaz-Parra et al., 2022).
5. **Big Data:** Big Data is invented by the giants of the web and presents itself as a solution designed to provide teachers and learners a real-time access to giant databases. It refers to the evolution and use of technologies that provide the right user at the right time with the right information from a mass of data that has been growing exponentially for a long time in the society. Big Data defines a category of techniques and technologies used in the analysis of complex datasets. Big Data has velocity, veracity, volume, variety and values as its attributes (Riahi & Riahi, 2018).
6. **Learning management system (LMS):** This is a software application or web-based technology used to plan, implement and assess a specific learning process. It's used for e-learning practices and, in its most common form, consists of two elements: a server that performs the base functionality and a user interface (UI) that is operated by instructors, students and administrators (Kirvan & Brush, 2024). LMS should be dynamic; that is, it should be active, flexible, customizable and adaptable. Whether a LMS is proprietary or open source, it will need to be capable of executing a variety of functions that work together to provide a seamless experience for the user. Course management, assessment, tracking progress, grade book, communication tools, security and privacy (Turnbull, Chugh & Luck, 2020).
7. **Smartboard:** This is also known as interactive whiteboard, interactive digital board, interactive display or interactive board. It is an advanced digital tool that operates interactively, either directly or through other devices, serving as a technological advancement over traditional whiteboards. Smartboards have always been used as a way for people to share messages, present information and engage in collaborative and idea development. With the same cooperative goals in mind, interactive whiteboards can connect to the internet and instantly digitize tasks and operations. Interactive whiteboards facilitate dynamic presentations, collaboration and educational demonstrations by combining the simplicity of a whiteboard with advanced technology. They enable real-time engagement and can connect to the internet, enhancing their functionality by integrating digital tasks seamlessly into group settings (Hanna, 2024).

Prospects of Smart Teaching and Learning in Tertiary Institutions

The emergence of smart education technologies or solutions powered by AI, learning analytics, algorithms and other technologies presents many opportunities. Smart technologies can improve education systems and education delivery by enhancing access to education, improving its quality for learners, and enhancing its cost efficiency for societies (Vincent-Lancrin, 2022).

Smart teaching and learning are usually effective. One of the key promises of smart technologies is to enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning for better student learning. Smart education and learning have made personalised teaching and learning possible. Personalised learning aims to provide all students with the appropriate curriculum or task and scaffold them within a task based on a diagnosis of their knowledge and knowledge gaps. Increasingly, this personalised learning, focusing on the "what," also considers how students learn and contemplate factors such as self-regulation, motivation, and effort (Díaz-Parra et al., 2022; Vincent-Lancrin, 2022).

Another significant prospect of smart teaching and learning is that it enhances students' engagement, which is the key to learning and solutions that keep students engaged within digital or physical learning environments are being developed to identify their affective states during learning and to nudge them toward re-engagement when they seem to disengage. Smart teaching and learning make it possible for educational content to be designed and tailored for the needs of students by considering their learning patterns (auditory, visual, blended and peer) (Turnbull, Chugh & Luck, 2020).

Smart teaching and learning also promote equity. There are many reasons to believe that smart technologies can advance the equity agenda. First, teaching and learning technology can expand access to learning opportunities. Smart technologies can reduce inequity by facilitating the inclusion of students with special needs and by adapting learning to different learning styles. Technology has, for example, made it much easier to support the diagnosis of learning difficulties such as dyslexia, dyscalculia, and dysgraphia, and remedial digital responses have also been developed. A variety of smart technologies applied to learning solutions also makes it easier for blind or visually impaired students, as well as deaf or hard-of-hearing students, to use assistive technologies to access learning materials and easily perform the educational tasks required by other students.

Efficiency in teaching and learning: efficiency is also about how teachers use their time, and smart technologies can free some of their time and allow them to focus on the most stimulating aspects of their work. An obvious example is formative assessment or developments in the automated grading of open-ended essays because grading and making assessments are time-intensive tasks when done manually. Another example is the diagnosis of special needs, which can now be supported by technology solutions. By freeing up time for teachers, smart technologies can allow them to give more time to learners who most need their attention and to focus on complex aspects of learning, including the acquisition of higher-order or socioemotional skills, or on their continuous professional development (Vincent-Lancrin, 2022).

Smart teaching and learning eliminates geographical barriers. In traditional teaching and learning, both the teachers and the learners were restricted to a physical space where they needed to present before teaching and learning could occur. However, with the advent of smart technologies deployed for teaching and learning, teachers delivered lectures, and learners accessed learning materials that may be superior to what they can access locally (Vincent-Lancrin, 2022; Kirvan & Brush, 2024).

Challenges of Smart Teaching and Learning in Tertiary Institutions

There is an abundance of literature and studies on the factors mitigating the effectiveness of digital/smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions. The reports of the literature are similar with most of them attributing the challenges of smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions to poor ICT/digital literacy skills, weak Internet connectivity, inadequate ICT infrastructure, fear of change, comfortability with the traditional teaching and learning patterns, inadequate funding of tertiary institutions and lack of priority of smart teaching and learning from the tertiary institution management (Saleh, 2019; David-West, 2022).

Another problem of smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions is inadequate or ineffective policy frameworks on smart teaching and learning. As things stand, Nigeria has enormous policies on education. However, it has been discovered that most of these policies have not been reviewed or upgraded to meet current realities. This makes the Nigerian educational system (which teaching and learning are a core part of) to be struggling for survival.

Case Studies

Smart teaching and learning are gaining prominence in this era dominated by the continuous evolution of technologies. With the rapid advancement of technologies, most institutions of learning are transitioning from traditional teaching and learning to technology-aided learning. Globally, there are

differences in smart teaching and learning. Thus, to create a context for this chapter, the case of smart teaching and learning at Kwara State University will be reported.

Smart teaching and learning have been gradually practised at Kwara State University since around 2017. This began with the use of smart boards for lectures, a website (<https://lms.kwasu.edu.ng>) for moderating the institution's general courses and an application software (KWASU Center for Entrepreneur) launched for seamless teaching and learning of entrepreneurship skills among the students.

The birth of COVID-19 in 2020 marked a significant revolution in the teaching and learning processes in tertiary institutions of learning across the globe. Kwara State University was not excluded from this necessitated shift. To respond to the challenge of COVID-19, Kwara State University has strategies to design a special website for teaching and learning, which will be incorporated with different teaching and learning platforms such as Google Classrooms, Zoom and the like. The school leveraged the website to make teaching and learning seamless for both her lecturers and students.

The Kwara State University website, known as KWASU LMS (Learning Management System), has modules with varied parameters that can be explored to take desired courses. It also allows lecturers to create course content, assign tasks to students and assess students' performance. On the part of the students, course contents created by the lecturers can be accessed and read by the students; they can also attend scheduled lectures, mark attendance and submit assignments. It has been discovered that the LMS, application and smart boards have brought new paradigms to the teaching and learning processes at Kwara State University. However, it is important to note that those paradigms are being challenged by many factors, including poor Internet bandwidth, irregular power supply, cost of Internet subscription, inadequate technological infrastructure, technophobia among the lecturers and students, encouraging impersonation in answering questions and assignments by the students and inadequate digital literacy skills.

Conclusion

Advancement in technologies has facilitated a massive paradigm shift from traditional teaching and learning to a more sophisticated one where teaching and learning can occur in alignment with the teachers' and learners' peculiarities. Studies have shown that some countries across the world have a meeting with this wind of change by making teaching and learning happen in seamless manners. This study, thus, explores the possibility of deploying smart teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions. Findings through literature revealed that Nigeria's tertiary institutions could deploy artificial intelligence, learning management systems, cloud computing, big data, learning analytics and internet-of-education-things for smart teaching and learning. This would enhance efficiency and effectiveness in teaching and learning, promote equity in teaching and learning, eliminate geographical barriers and strengthen students' engagement. However, these opportunities are yet to be fully seized because of some apparent problems in Nigeria's tertiary institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the literature studied, this paper hereby recommends that:

1. The Nigeria University Commission (NUC), Nigeria Board of Technical Education (NBTE), the Nigeria Board of Colleges of Education (NBCE), Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TetFund), Nigeria Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) and other stakeholders should intensify their efforts towards driving and sustaining technology-oriented teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions by adequately funding the institutions. This would allow Nigeria's tertiary institutions to be financially buoyant to acquire the required IT infrastructure for smart teaching and learning.

2. Bodies of academic staff (ASUU and ASUP) and other stakeholders should collaborate to train the academic staff on ICT/digital literacies necessary for smart teaching and learning. The training would expose the academic staff to different smart technologies they can use for smart teaching and equip them with the competencies and abilities to manage smart teaching and learning platforms.
3. Nigeria's regulatory bodies for education should design policy frameworks tailored to driving the efficiency and effectiveness of teaching and learning in Nigeria's tertiary institutions. The policies should consider the roles of the educators and learners, the infrastructure to be used for teaching and learning platforms, and the contents to be made available on the platforms.
4. Internet service providers should endeavour to partner with the management of tertiary institutions to provide adequate Internet infrastructure. This would enhance the speed and quality of bandwidth needed for smart teaching and learning.

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